

Control of Unintentionally Generated Low Frequency RF Fields

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Abstract: Radiated emissions and susceptibility requirements imposed in bands where intentional RF reception or transmission does not occur is problematical. It is often desired to compare radiated emissions with radiated susceptibility performance to assess system level compatibility. For both theoretical and practical measurement limitations, this is not realistic. A limit and test method are proposed which work around the present limitations and provide direct comparison of radiated emissions and radiated susceptibility performance, in those cases where only unintentional emissions and reception are of interest (non-tunable electronics).

INTRODUCTION

Radiated emissions limits are imposed upon equipment to protect intentional receivers from unintentional transmitters. Radiated susceptibility limits are imposed upon equipment to protect unintentional receivers from intentional transmitters. Unfortunately, it is believed by many that if radiated emission limits are not imposed, unintentional radiators could radiate or couple enough power to upset unintentional receivers. Also, many mistakenly assume that RE102 and RS103 are complementary requirements and in order to determine compatibility between equipment, a comparison between radiated emissions and radiated susceptibility test data is required. Therefore, in many cases, radiated emission and susceptibility limits are imposed to protect unintentional receivers from unintentional transmitters.

Cabling between equipment is a major source of radiated emissions and can also be a major receptor of electromagnetic energy.[1] The most important aspect of designing electromagnetically compatible systems, in the absence of tunable electronics, is cable-to-cable coupling or crosstalk. Because space science experiments often operate at very low signal levels, special protection is required to maintain the integrity of these signals. Because radiated emissions limits do not necessarily protect against cable-to-cable coupling and complexity of space systems (and other constraints) do not always allow for complete system level functional testing, a limit and test method for controlling cable-to-cable coupling is proposed. The new method would limit common mode currents on cable bundles (culprit circuits) to a level such that currents induced by culprit circuits onto victim circuits would be lower than the currents impressed onto the victim circuits during radiated susceptibility or bulk current injection testing.

DISCUSSION OF RADIATED EMISSIONS AND SUSCEPTIBILITY REQUIREMENTS

History of Radiated Emissions Requirements

Radiated emissions limits were first imposed to protect radio and navigation receivers on World War II era aircraft. These receivers utilized unshielded transmission lines between receiver and antenna. DC motors, ignition systems, power cabling and other unintentional radiators emitted RF noise which coupled onto the antenna lead-in and interfered with receiver operation.[2] Limits defined in the early electromagnetic interference (EMI) specifications appeared to be at radio receiver threshold of sensitivity and were imposed to protect voice receivers. Test methods which evolved were based on typical aircraft installations of the day.[3]

History of Radiated Susceptibility Requirements

In order to protect equipment from fields generated by intentional transmitters, radiated susceptibility limits were imposed. The unshielded antenna lead-ins used on early receivers were also used for transmitters. In the transmit mode, emissions leaking from these lead-ins could upset other avionics inside the aircraft. When the old fashioned transceivers were replaced with equipment utilizing coaxial antenna lead-ins, concern shifted to antenna generated fields.[2] The test method specified in MIL-I-6181B (1953), which shows a stub antenna mounted one foot from the equipment under test (EUT), is conducted inside a shielded enclosure. Resulting resonances due to the test chamber walls, floor, and ceiling, are similar to resonances found inside an aircraft fuselage.[4,2] This seems to reflect concern for leakage from antenna lead-ins internal to the aircraft. However, MIL-STD-462D (1993), mandates use of RF absorber material to reduce reflections inside the test chamber during radiated susceptibility testing.[5] Because reflections are minimized, the field intensity at the EUT is more uniform over the whole EUT and is similar to the field intensity from an antenna mounted outside the vehicle.

Comparison of Radiated Emissions and Radiated Susceptibility Limits

Looking at radiated emissions and radiated susceptibility limits reveals a wide margin between the limits. The radiated

susceptibility limit levied in MIL-STD-461D (RS103) is 20 V/m (146 dB μ V/m) from 10 kHz to 18 GHz for space platforms. Radiated emissions limit of MIL-STD-461D is 60 dB μ V/m at 10 kHz falling to 24 dB μ V/m at 2 MHz, remaining at 24 dB μ V/m until 100 MHz and rising to 69 dB μ V/m at 18 GHz.[6] This is an "apparent design margin" of at least 77 dB. This large margin is better represented in Figure 1. The left side of the figure shows the margins between unintentional receivers and intentional transmitters and the margins between intentional receivers and unintentional transmitters. The purpose of RS103 and RE102 is to protect these margins. The margin shown on the right side of the figure is the margin between unintentional transmitters and unintentional receivers. Protection of this margin and comparison of emissions and susceptibility data was never intended. The application guide for MIL-STD-461D has commentary concerning this comparison. "There is no implied relationship between this requirement [RS103] and RE102. The RE102 limit is placed primarily to protect antenna-connected receivers while RS103 simulates fields resulting from antenna transmissions."[6]

Figure 1. Radiated Margin Analysis [2]

RADIATED EMISSIONS/SUSCEPTIBILITY MECHANISM IN THE ABSENCE OF TUNABLE ELECTRONICS

Based on Figure 1, one could very well argue that it is impossible for unintentional transmitters to interfere with unintentional receivers. Unfortunately, this is not always true, especially for NASA payloads which have a high density of electronics with intermingled cabling. An understanding of the coupling mechanism between non-tunable electronics, radiated emissions testing, and radiated susceptibility testing can explain how this interference might be possible.

The military and NASA radiated susceptibility test setup utilizes a transmitting antenna placed one meter from the EUT. The field intensity is monitored at the EUT and

measures are taken to ensure that the EUT is immersed within a uniform electric field during testing.[5] Radiated emissions testing employs a receiving antenna spaced one meter from the EUT. Given the electric field measured at one meter, it is difficult to determine the electric field at distances closer than one meter.

In the absence of tunable electronics, the most important aspect of designing electromagnetically compatible systems is cable-to-cable coupling or crosstalk. In low impedance circuits (loop impedance less than 377 Ω), inductive coupling is the primary coupling mechanism.[7] Crosstalk from a culprit circuit to a victim circuit could couple a large amount of noise onto the victim, causing interference. Crosstalk is dependent on the mutual inductance and mutual capacitance between the culprit and victim, as well as the loop impedance of each circuit. Inductive crosstalk, which can still occur when either the culprit or victim, or both are shielded and grounded at both ends, is dependent upon current flow, i.e., the magnetic coupling predominates.[1] Radiated electric field emissions testing in frequency bands below HF do not efficiently measure the magnetic field from cabling. This is because the antenna used over much of the frequency range below 100 MHz is the 104 cm rod antenna, and this antenna is sensitive to voltages appearing on the EUT and cables under test (CUT). However, the antenna impedance is poorly matched to the magnetic component of the field, and the antenna is unable to extract a large amount of energy from the magnetic field. [8,9]

At the present time, there is no military or NASA standard limit or test method to determine cable-to-cable coupling. In the majority of cases, none is required. Space science experiments, however, often operate at very low signal levels, requiring special protection. Although a system functional test can determine whether cable coupling is a concern, as NASA programs become more and more complex, complete system functional testing is becoming more difficult, if not impossible. Also, the time to find such problems is preferably prior to integration of hardware. For NASA spacecraft avionics and payloads, it is important to determine a test method and limit to control cable-to-cable coupling.

A test method and limit that could be substituted for RE102 in the frequency range below 100 MHz (historically, NASA has not utilized radio transceivers below 100 MHz), protect sensitive electronics from crosstalk, and provide direct comparison to CS114 and RS103 would lessen the design impact and lower the number of waivers processed per mission. Additionally, the test method should preferably be facilitated using presently available test equipment and also be non-intrusive.

TEST METHOD AND LIMIT

Rationale for Limit

In order to protect sensitive non-tunable electronics, such as scientific payloads, from unintentional radiators, a limit that can be compared with the payloads susceptibility data is

desired. CS114 of MIL-STD-461D was developed to augment RS103 testing. The purpose of the test is to inject noise currents on interconnecting cable bundles. The limit is directly related to currents induced on cabling during radiated susceptibility testing. The relationship of this limit to RS103 is that current coupled to cabling during RS103 is 1.5 mA per V/m, derived from worst-case measurements on aircraft.[6]

Assume that sensitive equipment and its cabling has demonstrated a level of injected cable current immunity by passing CS114 and/or RS103. Then the most noise current that could be coupled from other cabling onto the sensitive cabling without causing interference would be equivalent to the current injected during current injection testing. Lowering the amount of crosstalk induced current by some margin, say 6 dB, provides a design margin between crosstalk induced noise and noise induced during susceptibility testing.

By limiting bulk (common mode) current emissions on cable bundles, the current coupled to sensitive cabling can be limited to levels below CS114 amplitudes. This bulk current emission (BCE) limit can also be directly compared with the CS114 or RS103 limits.

Description of Test Method

The test method employs a current probe and a spectrum analyzer or EMI receiver. The cable bundles are placed on 5 cm standoffs. The current probe is clamped around the cable bundles and the common mode current is measured. The measurements are then compared against the BCE limit.

DEVELOPMENTAL TESTS AND RESULTS

Test Setup

Figure 2 is a schematic of the cable coupling test setup. Coaxial cables of approximately 1.4 meters were placed on 5 cm non-conductive standoffs. The cables were connected to BNC connectors and attached to chassis-mount connectors bonded to the ground plane by aluminum “L” brackets at each end. The outer conductor of the coax represented scientific payload cabling with shields terminated to ground at each end. NASA equipment and payloads are usually required to employ cabling in which signal lines and power lines are twisted with

their respective returns and cable shields are grounded at each end, preferably by peripheral termination to RFI backshells.[10,11] The spacing between the cabling was adjusted so that the common run of cabling was 1m. The cables were initially placed adjacent to each other, and then adjusted for 2 cm and 5 cm separations for later testing. Using a bulk current injection (BCI) probe, a signal generator and a power amplifier (at frequencies of 1 MHz and greater), a current was injected onto a culprit circuit. The culprit current and the current coupled onto the victim circuit were monitored using a current probe and computer-controlled spectrum analyzer.

Coupling Factor Testing

In order to determine the cable coupling factor (ratio of current coupled into victim to culprit current), a constant voltage was applied to the current probe and the signal was swept over the frequency range of 10 kHz to 100 MHz. Both the current in the culprit (injection) circuit and the victim circuit were monitored and compared to determine the coupling factor. This was done for a 0 cm (adjacent cables) separation distance, a 2 cm separation distance, and a 5 cm separation distance. Figure 3 shows an example of the measured current for the culprit and the victim circuits at 5 cm separation. The ratio of the culprit current to the victim current is the cable coupling factor. Figure 4 shows the coupling factor data for adjacent cables, cables with 2 cm separation, and cables with 5 cm separation. Above the resonant frequency of the cable, the cable coupling is assumed to be 0 dB, i.e., the current induced onto the victim circuit is equivalent to the current on the culprit circuit, although at some frequencies the data appears to show a small current gain on the victim. For frequencies above where the cable length is greater than 1/10 of a wavelength, the amplitude of the measured current is dependent on the positioning of the current probe along the cable due to standing waves along the cable. In this particular test setup, it was difficult to move monitoring probes to determine peak current amplitude. However, it is inconceivable that the culprit could transfer more energy to the victim than was present on the culprit. Therefore, for circuits in which the loop impedances are similar, it is assumed that the current coupled to the victim could not be greater than the current on the culprit.

- 1 Bulk current injection (BCI) Probe
- 2 Culprit cable current probe
- 3 Victim cable current probe
- 4 Foam standoffs, 5 cm
- 5 Braided shield cable
- 6 360° shield termination

Figure 2. Cable Coupling Test Setup

Figure 3. Measured Culprit and Victim Current, 5 cm separation

Figure 4. Cable Separation Coupling Factor

Figure 5. CS114 Calibration Curve and Injected Current Per MIL-STD-462D Test Method

Bulk Current Emissions Limit

Figure 5 shows the CS114 calibration limit (curve #3) less 6 dB. Also shown in the same figure is the current injected onto the culprit circuit per MIL-STD-462D. Note that due to the low impedance of the shield circuit (as compared to the 50Ω of the calibration circuit), the current tends to be greater than the calibration curve and is restricted by the specification current limit between 500 kHz and 15 MHz. If this current were to couple onto the victim circuit without attenuation, then the current would still be 6 dB below the CS114 limit. Figure 6 shows the same injected current with a potential BCE limit (0 dB coupling factor assumed). Also shown in the same figure are potential BCE limits relaxed for various cable separations.

Radiated Testing

Figure 7 shows the test setup used during radiated emissions testing. This test setup is similar to the one used in the coupling factor testing. The purpose of this test was to measure the radiated emissions from a culprit circuit that equaled the BCE specification shown in Figure 6. The culprit circuit was injected with a current amplitude that equaled the BCE limit and the radiated emissions from the circuit were measured with the 104 cm rod and biconical antenna. The radiated emissions from the culprit are shown in Figure 8 and plotted with the radiated emission limits from MIL-STD-461D, MSFC-SPEC-521B, and Shuttle ICD 2-19001. This implies that an unintentional transmitter can fail RE102 in the HF bands and higher and still not harm unintentional receivers (i.e., sensitive scientific experiments). It also implies that in the VLF and LF bands, while passing RE102, a circuit could potentially harm a sensitive circuit through cable-to-cable coupling.

Figure 6. BCE Limit and Relaxed Limits for Various Cable Separations

Figure 7. Radiated Emissions Test Setup

Figure 8. Radiated Emissions and Comparison to Various Limits

CONCLUSIONS

Because of the unique nature of scientific payloads, protection of these payloads from unintentional radiators is sometimes needed to ensure proper operation and successful completion of mission. The noise that is coupled to these sensitive circuits can be controlled by limiting the amount of noise present on adjacent cable bundles. This limit tends to be less stringent than RE102 and more suited to protect against cable-to-cable coupling. Figure 9 shows the proposed protection band for the BCE limit and how it augments RE102 and complements CS114 and RS103.

The limit proposed herein is not etched in stone. More work will be required to understand the crosstalk process and how cabling with high loop impedance can affect cabling with lower impedance. However, this limit and test method can be used as is in trying to determine compatibility for payloads that exceed RE102 limits.

Figure 9. Schematic of Limit Protection Bands

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